

The mite population reached its peak ($\bar{x} = 2485 + 306/3$ leaves) during the May-Jun premonsoon period and was lowest ($\bar{x} = 128 \pm 42/3$ leaves) during the late Nov-Dec postmonsoon period.

A. saccharini preferred relatively young, greenish foliage, with this order of preference—maximum tillering > panicle initiation > seedling > ripening stage (see table). It was most abundant in the middle to apical one-third stratum of the dorsal leaf surface. □

Effect of plant age on relative abundance and vertical distribution of *A. saccharini* on rice in the Philippines. IRRI, May-December 1990.^a

Plant stage (age) ^b	Adults and immatures (no.) on leafblade					
	Dorsal surface			Ventral surface		
	Apical third	Mid-third	Lower third	Apical third	Mid-third	Lower third
Seedling (18 DT)	27 ± 11 c	81 ± 52 c	16 ± 8 c	42 ± 18 c	15 ± 10 c	6 ± 4 c
Maximum tillering (45 DT)	1024 ± 137 a	1485 ± 186 a	434 ± 25 a	211 ± 22 a	723 ± 68 a	301 ± 48 b
Panicle initiation (60 DT)	456 ± 37 b	812 ± 72 b	168 ± 30 b	85 ± 36 b	644 ± 96 b	594 ± 176 a
Ripening (110 DT)	0	C	0	c	0	c
					8	5 c
						18 ± 6 c

^aAv of 10 replications. In a column, values followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level by LSD. ^bDT = days after transplanting.

A quadrat insect sampler for direct seeded rice

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Direct seeding pregerminated rice is gaining popularity in many rice-growing areas. Entomologists need a sampling device equivalent to the rice hill used for sampling in transplanted rice cultures. In direct seeded rice, single plants are hard to distinguish and have few tillers.

In the Philippines, a rice hill normally occupies 400-500 cm² at 20- × 20- or 20- × 25-cm hill spacing. We developed a sampler based on crop area.

A simple quadrat, constructed from flat metal bars, is fastened to an anchoring bar with a wing nut screw (see figure). The anchoring bar allows the quadrat to be raised as the crop grows.

The quadrat is rectangular rather than square to allow plants to be more easily grasped by hand and facilitates counting tillers, leaves, and insect pests. The quadrat will cover 0.05-m² sampling area, so that 20 samples equal 1 m².

The anchoring bar is jabbed into the soil at randomly chosen points in the field. The quadrat is attached with its leading side open. Once the quadrat is firmly anchored, the notched front bar is fitted into place to enclose the sample plants.

We have used this approach to sample stem borer egg masses, dead-hearts and whiteheads, and leaves damaged by leaf feeders. Direct counts of less mobile insects can also be made. □

The quadrat sampler.

Farming systems—deepwater rice

Cropping patterns for deepwater rice environments

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In North Bihar, 60% of the rice area is classified as deep water, where crops are

never assured. Under such situations, farmers can grow only one rice crop, in the rainy season.

Farmers have adopted various cropping sequences to minimize risks. We evaluated the suitability and economics of some rice-based cropping patterns for the deep water ecosystem of North Bihar.